

CAUTION! A SPIDER'S TRAP! A VISUAL METAPHOR POTENTIAL IN HUMAN TRAFFICKING AWARENESS

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Abstract. This paper explores the potential of using the spiderweb metaphor to support educational programs on awareness of human trafficking. The methods of conceptual analysis and empirical studies showed how the metaphor can shape students' perceptions of human trafficking. The results of the experiments with 60 undergraduates reveal that texts deliberately featuring spiderweb metaphors significantly improve emotional engagement and awareness. The study suggests that integrating graphical representations of the metaphor in educational materials can effectively raise awareness of human trafficking, particularly among young people in Ukraine, and proposes further research to evaluate broader impacts.

Keywords: visual metaphor, spiderweb, human trafficking, raising awareness, education.

Introduction. This paper focuses on the potential of using a *spiderweb* visual metaphor to support educational programs on awareness of human trafficking. It considers the possibility of developing graphical design solutions to enhance the effects of *spiderweb*-associated metaphors in media texts on students for primary prevention interventions. Human trafficking takes multiple forms including recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt of people through force, fraud, or deception, to exploit them for profit. Any person irrespective of their origins or social background can become a victim of this crime (*Human-Trafficking* n.d.). Since the full-scale Russia-Ukraine war Ukrainian citizens have become vulnerable to the potential danger of getting into the human trafficking situation in the hope of going safely abroad. However, for predators and human traffickers, the war in Ukraine is not a tragedy, it is an opportunity. Traffickers prey on vulnerabilities.

According to the Law of Ukraine “On Counteracting Human Trafficking”, local self-government bodies, enterprises, institutions, organisations, and individual citizens shall implement measures to prevent and combat human trafficking (*On Counteracting Human Trafficking*, n.d.). As an educator and researcher, the author strives to change student mindsets towards more careful border-crossing and job-seeking abroad. The integration of linguistic and non-linguistic disciplines in a joint commitment to contribute to social change is based on the studies of the cognitive mechanisms of shaping public opinion on the human trafficking situation and empirical research on the perceptions of spiderweb metaphor among students of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University. This article is a follow-up review of the data obtained, results received, and prospects for developing project solutions regarding the danger of human trafficking represented with graphical means to be used in educational interventions and social advertising.

Literature Review. From linguistics and social sciences to computer and technical research, the potential of visual tools to communicate social messages through visual metaphors has been studied. The social impact of metaphors is multifaceted. Modern metaphor studies have shifted from viewing metaphors merely as tools for understanding the world to recognising their potential to shape social behaviours. Emphasis is increasingly placed on reevaluating metaphors’ roles in social contexts (Julich-Warpakowski and Jensen, 2023) and optimising their use to meet societal needs. This field thrives on transdisciplinary collaboration, linking metaphor research to socially significant areas such as social sciences (Leezenberg, 2009; Ghazinoory and Aghaei, 2023), healthcare (Jayan and Alathur, 2021; Deng et al., 2022), public health (Dada et al., 2021), and social care (Siddiqi and Khan, 2022, Jen et al., 2022). Metaphors are increasingly valued as tools for uncovering implicit knowledge and experiences (Petrucijová and Glumbíková, 2021), offering fresh perspectives for social work and education practices.

As an applied research domain, metaphors serve as mechanisms for moderating social behaviour and shaping public opinion. They establish meaningful connections with fields such as law (Hanne and Weisberg, 2018), economics (Zhu 2023), psychology (Landau et al., 2011; De Saint Preux and Blanco 2021), cross-border security and migration (De Backer and Enghels, 2022), military strategy (Al-Muttairi, 2022), media communication (Flusberg et al., 2018, Hullman and Kwiatkowski, 2021), and education (Spours et al., 2022), among others. Metaphors are also essential when traditional methods fail to address specific challenges, such as social care or pressing societal issues.

Main text. A conceptual analysis of 600 media texts revealed a *spiderweb*-like construal of human trafficking. Human trafficking is depicted as a highly organised system of spatial interrelations among various actors, with the victim positioned at the centre. It is shaped by the intricate interrelations among all actors involved in the human trafficking scenario: *family members, law enforcement agencies, governments, and international NGOs* as complicit actors, either as *traffickers* or as *clients*. The

mental image evokes the visual resemblance of a *spiderweb*, where the connections between actors resemble web threads, and the actions of these actors converge on the victim, akin to a spider's prey (Paliichuk, 2011).

The theory of five frames was used to model the construal (Zhabotyńska, 2010). These five core frames are the *Thing Frame*, *Action Frame*, *Possession Frame*, *Identification Frame*, and *Comparison Frame*, each consisting of iterative units of meaning. For example, in the *Thing Frame*, the qualitative, quantitative, locative, temporative (time parameter), and mode of existence propositions were modeled. The *Action Frame* was modeled through the interrelation of state, process, contact, causation, agent-affected, result, and consequence propositions. The *Possession Frame* contains the part-whole, inclusion, and ownership propositions. The *Identification Frame* included personification, classification, and characterization propositions; within the *Comparison Frame*, the relations of identity, similarity, and likeness were also analysed, which contributed to uncovering the foundation for the metaphorical projections of human trafficking through the *spiderweb* image. Figure 1 illustrates the victim at the center, emphasising the actor's passivity and the stable interrelationships of the actors. Simultaneously, governments were represented through modal verbs such as *should*, *will*, and *must*, while law enforcement and NGOs were portrayed as ineffective bodies or even as "helpers" of traffickers. These frames were utilised to construct the conceptual spaces of the actors, defined as "a collection of one or more quality dimensions" (Boden, 2009) relevant to each actor in human trafficking conceptual situations.

Figure 1.

This construal is manifested in the corpus of 109,876 words (4,877 sentences) (skeli/spiderweb) generated with the Sketch Engine text analysis software. For instance, it reveals as follows: *The spider web of human trafficking; 'I'm like a fly trapped in a spider's web,'; ... the victim is caught in the spider's web; As a spider spins its web, catches its prey, wraps it, and waits for it to die, a trafficker lures and catches its*

victim, spins a mental and physical **trap** around them, waiting for their spirit to break so they can take full advantage of their bodies; Victims of human trafficking have compared the feeling of being **trapped in a spider web**.

Results. The conceptual, stylistic, and corpus analyses used in the previous studies predetermine the conceptual prerequisites of using *spiderweb* metaphors in educational interventions in an academic setting. An experiment was conducted to verify the effect of students' perceptions and assess the social impact of metaphor. 60 undergraduates from Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University, grouped into three cohorts, participated in the surveys during the ongoing 2022-2023 academic year. The case study covered four media fragments applied in three modes: *authentic* (the texts were used in the original), *weakened* (metaphors in the texts were replaced with neutral descriptions), and *enhanced* (the texts were complemented with metaphors). In total twelve variables were tested. The *Paired Samples T Test*, which measures the responses before and after participants are exposed to experimental conditions, revealed the changes in student post-reading perceptions, with the highest response to *enhanced* texts. They identify with trafficked people; imagine themselves being in the same situation; imagine sounds/voices; and state their being emotionally affected. Used for the differences between authentic –weakened; authentic–enhanced; and weakened–enhanced, the *Independent Samples T Test*, used for measuring the differences in perceptions between cohorts of participants, revealed the higher degrees for *imagining oneself being enslaved in the human trafficking situation; being isolated; emotionally affected; and being more careful about personal safety*, which points to the feasibility of the use of the *spiderweb* metaphor in designing anti-trafficking educational content (Paliichuk, 2023).

Discussion. The results of the conceptual and empirical studies induce further research on assessing the potential of using the *spiderweb* metaphor more explicitly by inserting respective graphical images in educational materials thus enhancing the effectiveness of alternative means of raising awareness of human trafficking among young people in Ukraine. The limitations refer mainly to the restricted size of the sample from one university and to the fact that, currently, the students experience greater emotional pressure and stress living in danger and threats related to the war in Ukraine. Collaboration between Ukrainian universities can mitigate this lack of a larger sample and diversify the audience regarding age, gender, and major disciplines.

Conclusion. The results uncover the properties of the *spiderweb* metaphor in structuring the reading experiences within the contours of the spiderweb-like construal. Metaphors used in the experimental texts can evoke the feeling of co-presence within the human trafficking situation. At the same time, a prospective study should include surveying students using visual representations of the *spiderweb* metaphor in educational materials to raise awareness of human trafficking among young people.

References

1. Al-Muttairi, B. (2022). Defining social, and cultural forces in the Arab world in the postwar. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.7056024
2. Boden, M. A. (2009). Conceptual Spaces. In *Springer eBooks*, 235–243. DOI : 10.1007/978-1-4020-9877-2_13
3. Dada, S., Ashworth, H., Bewa, M. J., & Dhatt, R. (2021). Words Matter political and gender analysis of speeches made by heads of government during the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMJ Global Health*, 6(1), e003910. DOI : 10.1136/bmjgh-2020-003910
4. De Backer, L., & Enghels, R. (2022). The persuasive potential of metaphor when framing Mexican migrants and migration. *Metaphor and the Social World*, 12(2), 204–223. DOI : 10.1075/msw.21001.bac
5. De Saint Preux, A. D., & Blanco, O. M. (2021). The power of conceptual metaphors in the age of pandemic: The influence of the WAR and SPORT domains on emotions and thoughts. *Language & Communication*, 81, 37–47. DOI : 10.1016/j.langcom.2021.08.003
6. Deng, Y., Yang, J., Wang, L., & Chen, Y. (2022). The Road Less Traveled: How COVID-19 patients use metaphors to frame their lived experiences. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(23), 15979. DOI : 10.3390/ijerph192315979
7. Flusberg, S. J., Matlock, T., & Thibodeau, P. H. (2018). War metaphors in public discourse. *Metaphor and Symbol*, 33(1), 1–18. DOI : 10.1080/10926488.2018.1407992
8. Ghazinoory, S., & Aghaei, P. (2023). Metaphor research as a research strategy in social sciences and humanities. *Quality & Quantity*. DOI : 10.1007/s11135-023-01641-8
9. Hanne, M., & Weisberg, R. (2018). Narrative and metaphor in the law. In *Cambridge University Press eBooks*. DOI : 10.1017/9781108381734
10. Hullman, G. A., & Kwiatkowski, M. (2021). Social constructions of conflict and mediation as factors in mediation program decisions. *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*. DOI : 10.1002/crq.21325
11. *Human-Trafficking*. United Nations: Office on Drugs and Crime. <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/human-trafficking/human-trafficking.html>
12. Jayan, V., & Alathur, S. (2021). Military & War Metaphor during Covid-19 in India. *Proceedings of the 2021 6th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Security, ICCCS 2021*. DOI : 10.1109/icccs51487.2021.9776329
13. Jen, S., Brandt, G., Carr, K., Riquino, M. R., Cole, S., & Pacey, M. S. (2022). “I Don’t Know What World I Live in Anymore”: Social work student narratives of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Qualitative Social Work*, 147332502211143. DOI : 10.1177/14733250221114389
14. Julich-Warpakowski, N., & Jensen, T. W. (2023). Zooming in on the notion of *metaphoricity*. *Metaphor and the Social World*, 13(1), 16–36. DOI : 10.1075/msw.00027.jul
15. Landau, M. J., Vess, M., Arndt, J., Rothschild, Z. K., Sullivan, D., & Atchley, R. A. (2011). Embodied metaphor and the “true” self: Priming entity expansion and protection influences intrinsic self-expressions in self-perceptions and interpersonal behavior. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 47(1), 79–87. DOI : 10.1016/j.jesp.2010.08.012
16. Leezenberg, M. (2009). From Cognitive Linguistics to Social Science: Thirty Years after *Metaphors We Live By*. *Cognitive Semiotics*, 5(1–2), 140–152. DOI : 10.1515/cogsem.2013.5.12.140
17. Paliichuk, E. (2011). Linguistic and Conceptual Peculiarities of Human Trafficking Situation in Modern English-Language Media Discourse [Unpublished MA thesis]. National Kyiv University.

18. Paliichuk, E. (2023) “A spiderweb of human trafficking: An empirical linguistic study”, *Crossroads. A Journal of English Studies*, (43), pp. 124–155. DOI : 10.15290/CR.2023.43.4.07
19. Petrucijová, J., & Glumbíková, K. (2021). Metaphors as a tool for understanding of lived experience of social work practitioners in the contemporary Czech society. *British Journal of Social Work*. DOI : 10.1093/bjsw/bcab075
20. Siddiqi, B., & Khan, N. N. (2022). Social Stigma and Suffering: Perceptions, Practices and Impacts around COVID-19 in Bangladesh. *South Asia Multidisciplinary Academic Journal*, 29. DOI : 10.4000/samaj.8253
21. Spours, K., Grainger, P., & Vigurs, C. (2022). ‘We are all in the same storm but not in the same boat’: the COVID pandemic and the Further Education Sector. *Journal of Education and Work*, 35(8), 782–797. DOI : 10.1080/13639080.2022.2149715
22. Zhabotynska, S. A. (2010). Principles of building conceptual models for thesaurus dictionaries. *Cognition, Communication, Discourse*, 1, 75–92. DOI : 10.26565/2218-2926-2010-01-05
23. Zhu, M. (2023). A Cognitive Analysis on Conceptual Metaphors in English Economic Discourse. *English Language Teaching and Linguistics Studies*, 5(2), p.93. DOI : 10.22158/eltls.v5n2p93
24. *On Counteracting Human Trafficking. The Law of Ukraine. / Про протидію торгівлі людьми.* Офіційний Вебпортал Парламенту України.
<https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3739-17#Text>